

Ukrainian Conference with International Participation

**«CHEMISTRY, PHYSICS
AND TECHNOLOGY OF SURFACE»**

and

Workshop

**«MICROWAVES AND NANOPARTICLES
FOR REAL-TIME DETECTION
OF HUMAN PATHOGENS»**

(multinational research NATO SPS project G5798
«A novel nanoparticle based real-time sensor for
B. anthracis and *M. Tuberculosis*»)

*This workshop
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and Security Programme

**19-20 October 2022
Kyiv
Ukraine**

Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry
of National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Scientific Council

“Chemistry and Technology of Surface Modification”
Interbranch Scientific and Technical Complex “Surface Chemistry”

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TECHNOLOGY OF SURFACE”**

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DETECTION OF HUMAN PATHOGENS”**
(multinational research NATO SPS project G5798 «A novel nanoparticle based
real-time sensor for *B. anthracis* and *M. tuberculosis*»)

Book of abstracts

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Kyiv
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Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry of National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Scientific Council "Chemistry and Technology of Surface Modification"
Interbranch Scientific and Technical Complex "Surface Chemistry"

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Conference Program

October 19, Wednesday

9:00 – 9:45 Registration of participants

10:00 – 10:25 Opening of the Conference at the Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry of National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine

Academician of NAS of Ukraine, Professor M. Kartel

Oral Session 1

Chair: Professor M. Kartel

10:25 – 10:50 V.V. Turov, V.M. Gun'ko, T.V. Krupska, M.V. Borysenko. Cluster formation in NaOH solution at a surface of highly dispersive silica: environment effects (*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).

10:50 – 11:05 Group Photo

11:05 – 11:30 Coffee break

Oral Session 2

Chair: Professor V. Turov

11:30 – 11:55 V.M. Gun'ko. Morphological and textural features of various materials composed of porous or nonporous nanoparticles differently packed in secondary structures (*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).

11:55 – 12:15 V.F. Zinchenko, O.G. Ieriomin, G.V. Volchak, I.V. Stoianova, P.G. Doga, N.O. Chivireva. Spectroscopic study of the nanostructurization in frozen solutions-melts of NaCl – KCl + (EuF₃ – CeF₃) system (*O.V. Bogatsky Physico-Chemical Institute, NAS of Ukraine, Odesa*).

12:15 – 12:35 A.M. Kudin¹, L.A. Andryushchenko¹, V.G. Borisenko¹, M.M. Goroneskul¹, I. Wojtczak², W. Brzozowska³, E. Olewnik-Kruszkowska², M. Sprynsky². Thermal and fire resistance of luminescent coating on a base of silicon elastomer with diatomaceous biosilica filler (¹*National University for Civil Defence of Ukraine, Kharkiv*, ²*Nicolaus Copernicus University, Toruń, Poland*, ³*Institute of Marine and Environmental Sciences, University of Szczecin, Poland*).

12:35 – 12:50 A.P. Kusyak¹, A.L. Petranovska¹, S.P. Turanska¹, O.I. Oranska¹, Ya.M. Shuba², D.I. Kravchuk², L.I. Kravchuk², V.G. Nazarenko³, R.M. Kravchuk³, V.A. Dubok⁴, O.A. Bur'yanov⁵, V.S. Chornyi⁵, Yu.L. Sobolevs'kyi⁵, P.P. Gorbyk¹. X-ray luminescent nanodisperse crystalline lanthanum phosphate: synthesis, properties, application (¹*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*Bogomolets Institute of Physiology, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ³*Institute of Physics, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ⁴*Frantsevich Institute of Problems of Materials Science, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ⁵*Bogomolets National Medical University, Kyiv, Ukraine*).

74. **K.A. Korotkov**, A.M. Kasumov, V.M. Karavaeva, K.O. Vyshnevskaya, A.I. Ievtushenko, A.I. Dmitriev. **Boundary thickness of Ni island nanofilms for the tunneling mechanism of conduction** (*Frantsevich Institute for Problems of Material Science, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
75. **A.V. Korotun**^{1,2}. **Polarizability of metal nanobicone** (¹*National University Zaporizhzhia Polytechnic, Ukraine*, ²*G.V. Kurdyumov Institute for Metal Physics, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
76. **A. Kramar**¹, P. Kuzema¹, V. Anishchenko², O. Stavinskaya¹, N. Smirnova¹, R. Ivannikov³, I. Laguta¹, O. Linnik¹. **The plant extracts as the reducing agents in the processes of photocatalytic reduction of toxic dichromate ions** (¹*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*L.M. Litvinenko Institute of Physical-Organic and Coal Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ³*M.M. Gryshko National Botanic Garden, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
77. **M.V. Kravchenko**, I.V. Romanova. **Impact of synthetic routes on the porous structure and adsorption properties of magnesium silicates** (*Institute for Sorption and Problems of Endoecology, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
78. **D.A. Krysenko**, **Yu.I. Tarasevich**. **Thermodynamics of the ion exchange of Ca²⁺ and Sr²⁺ cations on Na-form of clinoptilolite** (*A.V. Dumansky Institute of Colloid Chemistry and Water Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
79. **K.O. Kudelko**¹, L.M. Rozhdestvenska¹, L.M. Ponomarova², V.M. Ogenko¹. **Porous AAO membrane prepared by anodizing aluminium in electrolyte: oxalic acid and carbon nanodots** (¹*Vernadsky Institute of General and Inorganic Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*Faculty of Technical Systems and Energy Efficient Technologies, Sumy State University, Ukraine*).
80. M.T. Kartel^{1,2}, **O.M. Lisova**², G.M. Gunya², P.P. Gorbyk², S.M. Makhno^{1,2}. **Electrophysical properties of nanostructured NiCo/BaTiO₃ and NiCo/TiO₂ composites** (¹*Ningbo Sino-Ukrainian New Materials Industrial Technologies Institute Co., Ltd, People's Republic of China*, ²*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
81. **V.I. Maksin**^{1,3}, R.V. Lavrik¹, T.I. Ushchapivska¹, O.V. Petrenko², A.M. Zaslavsky³. **On the question of obtaining single crystals of double sodium-manganese(II) dipyrophosphate in fluoride melts** (¹*National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine*, ³*Institute "Resource" of the State Agency "Reserve", Kyiv, Ukraine*).
82. I.P. Koziarskyi¹, M.I. Ilashchuk¹, I.G. Orletskyi¹, L.A. Myroniuk^{1,2}, **D.V. Myroniuk**^{1,2}, E.V. Maistruk¹, D.P. Koziarskyi¹. **Electrical properties of graphene/p-CdTe Schottky diodes fabricated by deposition of carbon films from polyvinylpyrrolidone aqueous solution** (¹*Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine*, ²*I.M. Frantsevich Institute for Problems of Materials Science, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
83. **L. A. Myroniuk**^{1,2}, D.V. Myroniuk^{1,2}, I.P. Koziarskyi¹, E.V. Maistruk¹, S.I. Kuryshchuk¹, A.I. Ievtushenko², I.M. Danylenko³, V.V. Strelchuk³, M.M. Solovan¹. **Mechanical exfoliation of graphite to graphene in polyvinylpyrrolidone aqueous solution** (¹*Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine*, ²*Frantsevich Institute for Problems of Materials Science, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ³*V.E. Lashkaryov Institute of Semiconductor Physics, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
84. **Y.A. Onanko**¹, D.V. Charnyi¹, A.P. Onanko², O.P. Dmytrenko², M.P. Kulish², T.M. Pinchuk-Rugal², A.M. Gaponov², A.A. Kuzmych², P.P. Ilyin². **Adsorption mechanical spectroscopy of nanocomposites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes and polyamide, polyvinyl chloride, polyethylene, foam polystyrene** (¹*Institute of Water*

Adsorption mechanical spectroscopy of nanocomposites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes and polyamide, polyvinyl chloride, polyethylene, foam polystyrene

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The characteristics of polymer nanocomposites, the dimensions of which are at least in one direction comparable to De-Broil wavelength for electrons, that is from several to hundreds of nanometers $\lambda_{DB} = 10 \div 100$ nm, fundamentally differ from the characteristics of macroscopically homogeneous systems. Concentration dependence of elastic modulus $E(C)$ of nanocomposite polyamide-6 (PA-6) $(\text{NH}(\text{CH}_2)_5\text{CO})_n$ + methylene dye blue squaring (DBSQ) in Fig., quasilongitudinal ultrasound velocities $V_{\parallel}$, which were determined from the oscillograms [1], and adsorption mechanical spectroscopy, internal friction Q^{-1} were studied.

Fig. Concentration dependence of elastic modulus $E(C)$ of nanocomposite polyamide-6 + DBSQ

Elastic modulus E , shear modulus G , Poisson coefficient μ , internal friction Q^{-1} are dependent from nanocomposite anisotropy.

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1. A.P. Onanko, V.V. Kuryliuk, Y.A. Onanko *et al.* J. Nano- Electron. Phys. **12**(4) (2020) 04026(1).